

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

Bulacan state university library: Innovative services to support distance learning during Covid-19 of S.Y. 2020-2022

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Abstract

This study aims to identify the Bulacan State University Library Services to Support Distance Learning during Covid-19 of 2020-2022. This research used documentary analysis of qualitative research in which documents are interpreted by the researchers to give voice and meaning around an assessment topic. Documents were assessed for their completeness; in other words, how selective or comprehensive the data is. Also of paramount importance upon evaluation of documents were the considerations that the data are “necessarily precise, accurate, or complete recordings of events that have occurred”. The study found that University Library provided and implemented eight new services such as: a.) Outdoor Library Book Return b.) Online Library Instruction c.) Online Book Request d.) Online Book Suggestion e.) Library and Information Research Assistance f.) Remote References and Information Access (RRIA) g.) Bulacan State University Library G-Site h.) Library Community Engagement.

Keywords: University library; Library service; Distance learning; Innovative library services

1. Introduction

The library's primary purpose is to utilize the collections owned effectively and efficiently. Furthermore, library services support educational activities by managing and providing information services [1]. Based on the Guidelines for The Implementation of School Libraries in Indonesia, there are minimal services that must be organized by school libraries, namely circulation services, reference services, and reading services [2]. However, libraries can develop other services according to the needs of the library. In principle, the school library service was developed based on the characteristics and needs of the library users [3].

Innovative library services are currently a challenge for libraries. Innovations in library services can develop libraries, especially for teaching and learning purposes [4]. The changing digital environment is driving service and practical transformation in libraries [5]. Information technology plays a vital role in the library services process [6] and can increase user expectations regarding new services [7] explains that libraries' innovations are tricky because of cost factors and the latest technology. However, the idea of innovation can grow from the creativity and enthusiasm of library staff. In line with the research results [8], school library funding is often inadequate so that libraries cannot run optimally. Responding to the pandemic, libraries in Indonesia also need to develop innovation and creativity in maintaining engagement and optimizing the role of libraries in distance learning. One form is to change the library program or service to be online-based [9]. However, distance learning has various challenges and impacts on library services such as administration, acquisitions, cataloging, collection access, references, and instructions and systems [10].

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This study aims to identify the Bulacan State University Library Services to Support Distance Learning during Covid-19 of 2020-2022. This study presents the Bulacan State University Library developed and implemented eight new services based on the needs of the faculty and students of the University as well as of the Community.

2. Methodology

The researchers utilized the documentary analysis in which documents are interpreted by the researchers to give voice and meaning around an assessment topic. Analyzing documents incorporates coding content into themes similar to how focus group or interview transcripts are analyzed. There is the question of how many documents the researcher should gather. Bowen suggests that a wide array of documents is better, although the question should be more about quality of the document rather than quantity [11]. Bowen adds that documents should be assessed for their completeness; in other words, how selective or comprehensive their data is. These issues are summed up in another eight-step process offered by O'Leary [12]:

- Gather relevant texts.
 - Develop an organization and management scheme.
 - Make copies of the originals for annotation.
 - Assess authenticity of documents.
 - Explore document's agenda, biases.
 - Explore background information (e.g., tone, style, purpose).
 - Ask questions about document (e.g., Who produced it? Why? When? Type of data?).
 - Explore content.
-

3. Result and Discussion

Covid-19 resulted to distance learning that requires learners to learn fully from home, with no in-person contact. The restriction of learner access to resources and decreased visibility/impact of the school library and library programming become the primary concern of school librarians during distance learning; administrators may tie the school librarian's work to the physical space of the library, devaluing their other roles and not seeing them as a crucial resource in an online environment.

The University Library can reach out to public libraries and other community organizations to combine efforts for a greater impact; think outside the box to meet your learner needs; set up regular communication channels to educators and to parents to highlight resources.

3.1. University Library New Services

3.1.1. Outdoor Library Book Return

Objectives

- To enable the Bulacan State University (BulSU) library users to return easily and safely the books borrowed.
- To facilitate the returning of borrowed books and materials without violating health protocols prescribed to prevent further transmission of COVID-19 infection

Rationale

This service is offered to let library patrons drop off their finished books and media in book drop boxes. Drop boxes are located at the main gate and 2nd gate of the university.

Figure 1 BulSU Library Online Outdoor Library Book Return

3.1.2. Online Library Instruction

Rationale

This service is designed to provide library orientation for the students and faculty.

Objectives

- To develop awareness among library patrons as regards to the Bulacan State University (BulSU) Library profile, its collections and its services in particular to the new normal
- To help the BulSU Library patrons in identifying, locating and accessing print and electronic resources provided by the BulSU Library.

Figure 2 BulSU Library- Online Library Instruction

3.1.3. Online Book Request

Rationale

OBR is one of the services provided by the Bulacan State University Library. It allows library clients to borrow books for home use, request for photocopying and scanning via email request and Google Forms. Library patrons who wish to avail this service can photocopy and scan up to 10% of one chapter of the book.

Objectives

- To enable the Bulacan State University (BulSU) library users to borrow books for home use; request for a photocopy and scanning purposes.
- To facilitate the borrowing of books without violating health protocols prescribed to prevent further transmission of COVID-19 infection

Figure 3 BulSU Library- Online Book Request

3.1.4. Online Book Suggestion

Rationale

Online Book Suggestion service is designed to gather information about the requested resources that are tailored fit to the needs of the stakeholders. Students and faculty may send their suggested books to be purchased via BulSU OPAC and/or via online forms and social media accounts.

Objectives

- To provide a venue for systematic book purchase recommendations by BulSU library patrons
- To facilitate receipt of recommendations from BulSU library clients through non-physical contact transactions in the effort to develop library collections

Figure 4 BulSU Library- Online Book Suggestion

3.1.5. Library and Information Research Assistance

Rationale

This service provides virtual assistance to library users to help them in their research needs. This may include requests for photocopying and scanning of research materials.

Objectives

- To enable the Bulacan State University (BulSU) library users to access our research collection.
- To facilitate the scanning of research materials and photocopying of abstract

Figure 5 BulSU Library- Library and Information Research Assistance

3.1.6. Remote References and Information Access (RRIA)

Rationale

This service provides virtual assistance to library users to help them in their information needs. This may include; answering Ready Reference Questions; providing Reader's Advisory Services; and Bibliographic Verification.

Objectives

- To enable the Bulacan State University (BulSU) Library to conduct virtually various reference assistance and services to different library patrons of the university in the new normal during this time of pandemic
- To respond to and address effectively the online queries of BulSU Library clientele through online means

3.1.7. Bulacan State University Library G-Site

Rationale

The site includes a wide variety of information which includes Open Educational Resources, open access databases, and current awareness services. It is made available online and can be accessed remotely.

Objectives

- To provide the Bulacan State University (BulSU) administration, faculty, staff and students remote access to various Open Educational Resources (OERs)
- To provide access to subscribed and open access databases
- To promote current awareness pertaining to library services

Figure 6 BulSU Library- Bulacan State University Library G-Site

3.1.8. Library Community Engagement

Rationale

This new service has been created because BulSU Library wants to put a new twist in the promotion of its services through social media platforms and to assure the user-community that this academic library is not only concerned about its collections and other physical facilities. Similarly, the BulSU Library is also after teaching and inculcating in the minds

of the user-community the passion and love for reading, the necessity to be information-literate, the need to be abreast with the current trends and most of all the need to learn the basic life hacks and simple instructions which can definitely help the people to be functional in the performance of their daily activities.

Objectives

- To keep up with the trends by creating new programs in the form of Edutainment
- To provide educational videos in promoting literacy

4. Conclusion

COVID-19 may have exacerbated the need for expanded access to academic resources, although it's been a reality many students and faculty have faced for the past years, and it won't suddenly disappear after the pandemic. What will evaporate, however, is the funding and determination to support the implemented online services of the library. Factors will eventually float as challenges to continue and expand needs and services libraries have taken on and should take on well due to the impact of Covid-19 in education system.

The opportunity for students to access school library materials is first dependent on having access to their library while studying at home. In time of crisis, our libraries have also been an engine of opportunity and in ways that defy the traditional characterization of the library as a place that only lends books and reading materials. University Library in partnership with the MIS department, were able to developed and implemented responsive services despite the absence of face to face or in-person contact to both students and faculty and even open its online services to the community.

Recommendation

With the development and provision of eight new services by Bulacan State University such as: a.) Outdoor Library Book Return b.) Online Library Instruction c.) Online Book Request d.) Online Book Suggestion e.) Library and Information Research Assistance f.) Remote References and Information Access (RRIA) g.) Bulacan State University Library G-Site h.) Library Community Engagement, the Library Services may:

- develop periodic monitoring if the services are fully utilized by the students and faculty.
- services are readily accessible at all time.
- online services are easy to use.
- online services are user friendly.
- Online services are responsive to recommendations and suggestions assistance form and feed-back forms.

Bulacan State University Library can reach out and tie-up to public libraries and other community organizations to combine efforts for a greater impact.

Compliance with ethical standards

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Disclosure of conflict of interest

This research paper underwent through the process of ethical considerations set by Bulacan State University in which the authors duly agreed and understands. The policies and procedures set in the University Research Manual of Bulacan State University were used as guide by the authors.

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